

Weaker Forms on Separation Axioms

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 21 June 2024	In general topology, the concepts of separation axioms play an important role. The main goal of this paper is to present the study of weaker forms of separation axioms called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-regular}$ and $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-normal}$ spaces using $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-open}$ sets in topological spaces. Further, the properties $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-compact}$, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-connected}$ and $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-Lindelof}$ spaces have been defined and studied their basic characterizations in topological spaces.
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1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES:

Njastad [8], in 1984 introduced and defined α -open sets. Following the work on α -open sets, many topologists focused on generalization of topological concepts using semi-open and α -open sets. These sets play an important role in the generalization of continuity in topological spaces. Maheshwari and Prasad [6] introduced s -normal spaces using semi-open sets. Nori and Popa [9], Dorsett [2], Arya [1] and Munshi [7] studied g -regular and g -normal spaces using g -closed sets in topological spaces.

In this paper, author establish the properties of weaker forms of separation axioms called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$ and $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$ spaces, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-regular}$ and $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-normal}$ spaces using $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ sets in topology. Also, we defined several properties related to them. Further, authors explained the properties of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-compact}$ spaces, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-connected}$ spaces, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-Lindelof}$ spaces in topological spaces and several properties related to them.

Definition 2.1. [4] A subset A of a TS R is said to be a semi generalized $\omega\alpha$ -closed (briefly $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$) if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is $\omega\alpha$ -open in R .

The family of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ subsets of a space R is denoted by $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$.

Definition 2.2. [4] The intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ sets containing a subset A of R is called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closure}$ of A and is denoted by $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(A)$.

A set A is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ if and only if $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(A) = A$.

Definition 2.3. [4] The union of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-open}$ sets containing a subset A of R is called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-interior}$ of A and it is denoted by $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-int}(A)$.

A set A is called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-open}$ if and only if $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-int}(A) = A$.

Definition 2.4. A function $f: R \rightarrow S$ is called a

(i) $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-continuous}$ [12] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ in R for every closed set V in S .

(ii) $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-irresolute}$ [12] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ in R for every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ set V in S .

(iii) $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-open}$ [12] if $f(V)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-open}$ in S for every open set V in R .

2. SPG ω A-SEPARATION AXIOMS

The weaker forms of separation axioms are found in this section, such as $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$ and $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$ spaces and their related concepts.

Definition 2.1: Let (R, τ) be a TS. Then R is said to be a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$ if for each $r_1, r_2 \in R^*$ with $r_1 \neq r_2$, there exists a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-open}$ set containing one but not the other.

Example 2.2: Consider $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_3\}\}$. The R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$.

Theorem 2.3: A space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$ iff $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closures}$ of distinct points are distinct.

Proof: Let $r_1, r_2 \in R$, where R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$. Then there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}O(R)$ with $r_1 \in U$, $r_2 \notin U$, and so $r_1 \notin R-U$ and $r_2 \in R-U$, where $R-U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C(R)$. We have, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$ is intersection of the $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-closed}$ sets, which contains r_2 .

Thus, $r_2 \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$. As, $r_1 \notin R-U$ and so $r_1 \notin \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_1\})$. Thus, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_1\}) \neq \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$. On the other hand, let $r_1, r_2 \in R$ holds for any pair of different points $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_1\}) \neq \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$. So, there exists at least one point $r \in R$ with $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_1\})$ and $r \notin \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$. Further, we have to prove that $r_1 \notin \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$. Let $r_1 \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$. Then, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_1\}) \subseteq \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$. So, $r \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$ which is a wrong. Thus, $r_1 \notin \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$ shows that $r_1 \in R - \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$ with R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-cl}(\{r_2\})$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set containing r_1 but not r_2 . Hence R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$.

Theorem 2.4: The property of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$ space is a hereditary.

Definition 2.5: A function $\Psi: R \rightarrow S$ is pre- $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open, if $\Psi(V)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open in R , for every $V \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$.

Theorem 2.6: Let $\Psi: R \rightarrow S$ be bijective, pre $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open. If R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$, then S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$.

Proof: Let Ψ be bijective, pre- $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open with R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$. Let $s_1, s_2 \in S$ with $s_1 \neq s_2$. Since Ψ is bijective, with $r_1, r_2 \in R$ with $\Psi(r_1) = s_1, \Psi(r_2) = s_2$. So, there exists $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set U such that $r_1 \in U, r_2 \notin U$. Thus, $\Psi(U^*)$ is $\text{spg}\omega$ -open set containing $\Psi(r_1)$ but not $\Psi(r_2)$. So, there exists $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set $\Psi(U) \in S$ such that $s_1 \in \Psi(U), s_2 \notin \Psi(U)$. Thus, S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$.

Theorem 2.7: The properties listed below are equivalent for a space R , where $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ is open under arbitrary union:

- (i) R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$,
- (ii) Each singleton set is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed,
- (iii) Each subset of R is the intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set containing it,
- (iv) The set $\{s\}$ is the intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set containing the point $r_1 \in R$.

Proof: (i) \rightarrow (ii): Let $r \in R$ with R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$. For each $s \in R$ with $s \neq r$, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R, s)$ but not r . Thus, $s \in U \subseteq \{r\}^c$. So, $\{r\}^c = \bigcup \{U : s \in \{r\}^c\}$, that is $\{r\}^c$ is the union of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets and so $\{r\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed.

(ii) \rightarrow (iii): Let (ii) holds and $A \subseteq R$. Then for each $s \notin A$, there exists $\{s\}^c$ with $A \subseteq \{s\}^c$ where $\{s\}^c$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open in R . We get, $A = \bigcap \{\{s\}^c : s \in A^c\}$ and so, the set A is the intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets containing A .

(iii) \rightarrow (iv): Proof is obvious.

(iv) \rightarrow (i): Let (4) holds and $r, s \in R$ with $r \neq s$. According to the assumption, there is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set U_r , with $r \in U_r, s \notin U_r$. Hence the condition of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$ space satisfied. Hence, R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$.

Definition 2.8: A space R is said to be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$ if for each pair of points r, s in R with $r \neq s$, there exists a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets U and V with the condition $r \in U, s \notin U$ and $s \in V, r \notin V$.

Example 2.9: Let $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_1\}, \{r_2, r_3\}\}$. The space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$.

Theorem 2.10: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$ space is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$ space.

Remark 2.11: The converse of the above examples does not hold from the following example.

Example 2.12: Let $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_1\}\}$. The space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_0$ but not $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$. There is no $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set G with $r_1 \in \{r_1\}$ and $r_2 \notin \{r_1\}$ holds for $r_1 \neq r_2$.

Theorem 2.13: A space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$ iff R has a singleton subset $\{r\}$ which is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed in R .

Proof: Let $r \in R$ and let $s \in \{r\}^c$. Then $s \neq r$, by R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$. So, there is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open set G such that $s \in G$ but $r \notin G$, that is for each $s \in \{r\}^c$, there exists $G \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ with $s \in G \subseteq \{r\}^c$. Thus, $\bigcup \{s : s \neq r\} \subseteq \bigcup \{G : s \neq r\} \subseteq \{r\}^c$. Thus, $\{r\}^c \subseteq \bigcup \{G : s \neq r\} \subseteq \{r\}^c$, that is $\{r\}^c = \bigcup \{G : s \neq r\}$. As, G is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open, then $\{r\}^c$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open in R and so, $\{r\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed in R .

On the other hand, let $r, s \in R$ be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed with $r \neq s$. Then $\{r\}^c, \{s\}^c$ are $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open with $s \in \{r\}^c$ but $r \notin \{r\}^c$ and $r \in \{s\}$ but $s \in \{s\}^c$. Then there are $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets $\{r\}^c$ and $\{s\}^c$ under $r \in \{s\}^c, s \in \{s\}^c$ and $s \in \{r\}^c, r \notin \{r\}^c$. So, R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$.

Theorem 2.14: Let $\Psi: R \rightarrow S$ be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C$, injective and S is T_1 . Then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$.

Proof: Let $r_1, r_2 \in R$ with $r_1 \neq r_2$. There exists $s_1, s_2 \in S$ with $s_1 \neq s_2$ such that $\Psi(r_1) = s_1$ and $\Psi(r_2) = s_2$. As S is $T_1, U, V \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(S)$, so that $s_1 \in U, s_2 \notin U$ and $s_1 \notin V, s_2 \in V$. That is $\Psi(r_1) \in U, \Psi(r_2) \notin U$ and $\Psi(r_1) \notin V, \Psi(r_2) \in V$. So, $r_1 \in \Psi^{-1}(U), r_2 \notin \Psi^{-1}(U), r_1 \notin \Psi^{-1}(V), r_2 \in \Psi^{-1}(V)$, where $\Psi^{-1}(U), \Psi^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ follows from $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}C$. Thus, if $r_1, r_2 \in R$ with $r_1 \neq r_2$, there exist $\Psi^{-1}(U), \Psi^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ such that $r_1 \in \Psi^{-1}(U), r_2 \notin \Psi^{-1}(U)$ and $r_1 \notin \Psi^{-1}(V), r_2 \in \Psi^{-1}(V)$. So, R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$.

Definition 2.15: Let R be TS . Then R is said to be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$ if there are disjoint $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets U, V with the condition $r \in U$ and $s \in V$ holds for each $r, s \in R$, where $r \neq s$.

Example 2.16: Let $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_1\}, \{r_2\}, \{r_1, r_2\}\}$. The space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$.

Remark 2.17: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$ space is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$. The converse of the implication is not true follows from the example.

Example 2.18: From Example 2.16, it is clear that the space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$ but not $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_1$.

Theorem 2.19: The intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed neighborhoods of each point of R is a singleton set if and only if the space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-}T_2$.

Proof: Let $r, s \in R$ where $r \neq s$. Then $U, V \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ such that $r \in U, s \in V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$, so $r \in U \subseteq R - V$ follows from the definition. Thus, $R - V$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed neighborhood of r excluding s . Hence, s not in the form part of intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed neighborhoods of r . As s is an arbitrary, the singleton set $\{r\}$ is the intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed neighborhoods of r .

On the other hand, let us consider r is the intersection of all $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed neighborhoods of any point $r \in R$ and y any arbitrary point of R with $r \neq s$. As s does not belong to the

intersection, there exists a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed neighborhood S of r with $s \notin S$. So, there exists $U \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(S)$ such that $s \in U \subseteq S$. Consequently, $U, R - S \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ under the condition $r \in U$ and $s \in R - S$ with $U \cap (R - S) = \emptyset$. Hence, R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-T}_2$.

Theorem 2.20: If $\Psi: R \rightarrow S$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}$, injective with S is T_2 , then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-T}_2$.

Proof: Consider two distinct points $r_1, r_2 \in R$. As Ψ is injective, there exists $s_1, s_2 \in S$ with $s_1 = \Psi(r_1)$ and $s_2 = \Psi(r_2)$. There exist $U, V \in \text{O}(S)$ with $U \cap V = \emptyset$ such that $s_1 \in U, s_2 \in V$ as S is T_2 . So, $r_1 \in \Psi^{-1}(U)$ and $r_2 \in \Psi^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$. Consider $\Psi^{-1}(U) \cap \Psi^{-1}(V) = \Psi^{-1}(U \cap V) = \Psi^{-1}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$. Thus, for each $r_1, r_2 \in R$ with $r_1 \neq r_2$, there are $\Psi^{-1}(U), \Psi^{-1}(V) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R)$ with $\Psi^{-1}(U) \cap \Psi^{-1}(V) = \emptyset$ with $r_1 \in \Psi^{-1}(U), r_2 \in \Psi^{-1}(V)$. Thus, R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-T}_2$.

3. SPG $\omega\alpha$ -REGULAR SPACES:

In this section we introduce the $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular spaces in topological spaces and obtained some of their properties.

Definition 3.1: A space R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular if there are open sets U, V such that $F \subseteq U, r \in V$ with $U \cap V = \emptyset$ holds for every $F \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$ and $r \in F$.

Remark 3.2: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular space is regular but not conversely.

Example 3.3: Consider $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_1\}, \{r_2, r_3\}\}$. Then R is regular but not $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular.

Theorem 3.4: Let R be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular and S is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed and open subset of R . The subspace S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular.

Proof: Let F be spg -closed subset of S with $s \in S - F$ and so $F \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$. Since R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular, there exist $U, V \in \text{O}(R)$ with $s \in U$ and $F \subseteq V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Thus $U \cap S$ and $V \cap S$ are disjoint open sets in S with $s \in U \cap S, F \subseteq V \cap S$. Thus, S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular.

Theorem 3.5: Let $\Psi: R \rightarrow S$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-I}$, bijective, open with R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular. Then S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular.

Proof: Let $F \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(S)$ with $s \in F$. For some point $r \in R$, let $s = \Psi(r)$. Then $\Psi^{-1}(s) \in R$ and $\Psi^{-1}(F) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$ as Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-I}$ where $r \in \Psi^{-1}(F)$. There $U, V \in \text{O}(R)$ with $r \in U, \Psi^{-1}(F) \subseteq V$ with $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Then, $s = \Psi(r) \in \Psi(U)$ and $F \subseteq \Psi(V)$. Thus, $\Psi(U), \Psi(V) \in \text{O}(S)$ such that $s \in \Psi(U), F \subseteq \Psi(V)$ where $\Psi(U) \cap \Psi(V) = \emptyset$ holds for all $s \in S$. Hence S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular.

Theorem 3.6: Let Ψ is pre $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open, closed, injective and S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular. Then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular.

Proof: Let $r \in R$ and $F \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$ with $r \in F$. As Ψ is pre $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open, $\Psi(F) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(S)$ such that $\Psi(r) \in \Psi(F)$. As S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular, $U, V \in \text{O}(R)$ such that $\Psi(r) \in U$ and $\Psi(F) \subseteq V$, that is $r \in \Psi^{-1}(U), F \subseteq \Psi^{-1}(V)$ with $\Psi^{-1}(U) \cap \Psi^{-1}(V) = \emptyset$. Thus, for each $r \in R$ and for every $F \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$ with $r \in F$, there exist $\Psi^{-1}(U), \Psi^{-1}(V) \in \text{O}(R)$ such that $r \in \Psi^{-1}(U)$ and

$F \subseteq \Psi^{-1}(V)$ with $\Psi^{-1}(U) \cap \Psi^{-1}(V) = \emptyset$. Thus, R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -regular.

4. SPG $\omega\alpha$ -NORMAL SPACES

In this section, we introduce the $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained some of their properties

Definition 4.1: A space R is said to be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal if for any disjoint $A, B \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$, there exist $U, V \in \text{O}(R)$ with $A \subseteq U, B \subseteq V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$.

Example 4.2: Consider $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_1\}, \{r_2\}, \{r_1, r_2\}, \{r_2, r_4\}, \{r_1, r_2, r_4\}, \{r_2, r_3, r_4\}\}$. Then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal.

Example 4.3: Let $R = \{r_1, r_2, r_3\}$ and $\tau = \{R, \emptyset, \{r_1\}, \{r_2, r_3\}\}$. Then R is normal but not $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal.

Theorem 4.4: A space R is normal if and only if there exists spg -open set $A \subseteq U \subseteq \text{cl}(U) \subseteq V$ holds for each closed set A and an open set V containing A .

Theorem 4.5: Let $\Psi: R \rightarrow S$ be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-I}$, bijective, open mapping and R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal. Then S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal

Proof: Let $A, B \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(S)$ with $A \cap B = \emptyset$. As Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-I}$, $\Psi^{-1}(A), \Psi^{-1}(B) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$. Then there exist $U, V \in \text{O}(R)$ with $\Psi^{-1}(A) \subseteq U$ and $\Psi^{-1}(B) \subseteq V$, as Ψ is open. As Ψ is bijective, $\Psi(U), \Psi(V) \in \text{O}(S)$ such that $A \subseteq \Psi(U)$ and $B \subseteq \Psi(V)$ with $\Psi(U) \cap \Psi(V) = \emptyset$. Hence S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal.

Theorem 4.6: Let R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal and S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed subset of R . Then the subspace S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal.

Proof: Let $A, B \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(S)$ with $A \cap B = \emptyset$. Then $A, B \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R)$. As R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal, there are $U, V \in \text{O}(R)$ such that $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq V$. As a result, $U \cap S, V \cap S$ are disjoint open subsets in the subspace S with $A \subseteq U \cap S, B \subseteq V \cap S$. Thus, S is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -normal.

5. SPG $\omega\alpha$ -COMPACTNESS

In this section, we introduce $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, countably $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact and $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -Lindelöf using $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets in TS and studied their properties.

Definition 5.1: A collection $\{B^*_i: i \in I\}$ of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets in a $TS R$ is called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover if $B^* \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in I} B^*_i$.

Definition 5.2: A $TS R$ is called $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact if every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R has a finite subcover.

Definition 5.3: A subset B^* of a $TS R$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact relative to R if for every collection $\{B^*_i: i \in I\}$ of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets of R with $B^* \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in I} B^*_i$ there exists a finite subset I_0 of

I such that $B^* \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in I_0} B^*_i$.

Definition 5.4: A subset B^* of a $TS R$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact if B^* is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact of the subspace of R .

Theorem 5.5: A $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed subset of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact relative to R .

Proof: Let $A^* \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}(R^*)$. Then $(R - A^*) \in \text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-O}(R^*)$.

Let $S = \{A^*_i; i \in I\}$ be a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of A^* by $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open subsets. Then $S^* = S \cup (R - A^*)$ is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover, that is $R = [\cup \{A^*_i; i \in I\}] \cup (R - A^*)$.

But, from hypothesis R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact and hence S^* is reducible to a finite subcover, say $S^* = R \cup A^*_{i_1} \cup A^*_{i_2} \cup \dots \cup A^*_{i_n} \cup (R - A^*)$, $A^*_{i_k} \in S^*$. Since $A^* \cap (R - A^*) = \emptyset$, so $A^* \subseteq A^*_{i_1} \cup A^*_{i_2} \cup \dots \cup A^*_{i_n} \in S$. Thus, a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover S contains a finite subcover and so A^* is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact relative to R .

Theorem 5.6: Let Ψ be surjective, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}$. If R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, then S is compact.

Proof: Let $\{A^*_i; i \in I\}$ be an open cover. Since Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}$, then $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i); i \in I\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R which has a finite subcover say $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i); i=1, \dots, n\}$.

Thus $R = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \Psi^{-1}(A^*_i)$, that is $\Psi(R) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n A^*_i$. As Ψ is

surjective, that is $S^* = \bigcup_{i=1}^n A^*_i$.

Thus $\{A^*_1, A^*_2, \dots, A^*_n\}$ is a finite subcover of $\{A^*_i; i \in I\}$. So, S is compact.

Theorem 5.7: If a function Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-I}$ and B be a subset of R which is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact relative to R , then $\Psi(B)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact relative to S .

Proof: Let $\{A^*_i; i \in I\}$ be any collection of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open sets in with $\Psi(B) = \bigcup_{i \in I} A^*_i$.

Then $B \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in I} \Psi^{-1}(A^*_i)$, where $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i); i \in I\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -

open in R . As B is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, there exists finite subcollection $\{A^*_1, A^*_2, \dots, A^*_n\}$ such that $B \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in I_0} \Psi^{-1}(A^*_i)$.

Thus $\Psi(B) \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in I_0} A_i$ and so $\Psi(B)$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact relative

to S .

Theorem 5.8: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space is compact.

Theorem 5.9: A TS R^* is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact if and only if every family of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed sets of R having finite intersection property has a non-empty intersection.

Proof: Suppose R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact and $\{A^*_i; i \in I\}$ be a family of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed sets with finite intersection property. We need to prove that $\bigcap_{i \in I} A_i \neq \emptyset$.

On the contrary $\bigcap_{i \in I} A_i^* = \emptyset$. Then $R - \bigcup_{i \in I} A^*_i = R$,

that is $\bigcup_{i \in I} (R - A^*_i) = R$.

The cover $\{R - A^*_i; i \in I\}$ is a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . As R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover $\{R - A^*_i; i \in I\}$ has a finite subcover, say $\{R - A^*_i; i=1, \dots, n\}$, that is $R = \bigcup_{i=1}^n (R - A^*_i)$, which implies that $R = R - \bigcap_{i=1}^n A^*_i$, that

is $R - R = R - \left[R - \bigcap_{i=1}^n A_i \right]$ and so $\emptyset = \bigcap_{i=1}^n A^*_i$. This

contradicts the assumption. Hence $\bigcap_{i=1}^n A^*_i \neq \emptyset$.

Other part, suppose every family of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed sets of R with finite intersection property has a non-empty intersection. To prove that R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact. Suppose R is not a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact. Then there exists a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover say $\{G_i; i \in I\}$ having no finite subcover. That is for any finite sub family

$\{G_i; i=1, \dots, n\}$ of $\{G_i; i \in I\}$, we have $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i \neq R$ which

implies that $R - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i \neq R - R$, and so $\bigcap_{i=1}^n (R - G_i) \neq \emptyset$.

Then the family $\{R - G_i; i \in I\}$ of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -closed sets has a finite intersection property. By assumption

$\bigcap_{i=1}^n (R - G_i) \neq \emptyset$, that is $R - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G^*_i \neq \emptyset$ and so

$\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i \neq R$. Hence $\{G_i; i \in I\}$ is not a cover of R , which

contradicts the fact that $\{G_i; i \in I\}$ is a cover for R . So, a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover $\{G_i; i \in I\}$ has a finite subcover $\{G_i; i=1, \dots, n\}$ and so R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact.

Definition 5.10: A TS R is said to be countably $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact ($C.\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact) if every countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R has a finite subcover.

Theorem 5.11: If R is a $C.\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space, then R is countably compact.

Proof: Let $\{A_i; i \in I\}$ be a countable open cover of R by open sets in R . Then $\{A_i; i \in I\}$ is $C.\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . As R is $C.\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, the countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R has a finite subcover, say $S = \{A^*_i; i=1, \dots, n\}$. Hence R is countably compact.

Theorem 5.12: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space is $C.\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact.

Theorem 5.13: If Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}$ from a $C.\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space R onto S , then S is countably compact.

Proof: Let $\{A^*_i; i \in I\}$ be a countable open cover of S . As Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha\text{-C}$, then $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i); i \in I\}$ is countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . Since R is $C.\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, the countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i); i \in I\}$ of R has a finite subcover say $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i); i=1, \dots, n\}$.

Thus $R = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \psi^{-1}(A^*_i)$ implies $\Psi(R) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n A^*_i$ and so $S =$

$\bigcup_{i=1}^n A^*_i$. Hence $\{A^*_1, A^*_2, \dots, A^*_n\}$ is a finite subcover for S ,

so S is countably compact.

Theorem 5.14: The image of a countably $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space under $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.I is $\text{C.spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact.

Proof: Let Ψ be a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.I from a $\text{C.spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space R onto S and $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ be a countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of S . Then $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i) : i \in I\}$ is a countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . Since R is $\text{C.spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, the countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i) : i \in I\}$ of R has a finite subcover say $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i) : i = 1 \dots n\}$. Thus $R = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \psi^{-1}(A^*_i)$, that is $\Psi(R) =$

$\bigcup_{i=1}^n A^*_i$ and so $S = \bigcup_{i=1}^n A^*_i$. So, S is $\text{C.spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact.

Definition 5.15: A TS R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -Lindelöf ($\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L) if every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R has a countable subcover.

Theorem 5.16: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L space is Lindelöf.

Proof: Let R be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L. Let $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ be an open cover of R and so $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open in R . As R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L, the $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ of R has countable subcover. Hence R is Lindelöf.

Theorem 5.17: Every $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact space is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L.

Proof: Let R be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact and $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ be $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . Then $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ has a finite subcover say $\{A^*_i : i = 1 \dots n\}$. Since every finite subcover is always a countable subcover and so $\{A^*_i : i = 1 \dots n\}$ is a countable subcover for R . Hence R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L.

Theorem 5.18: If Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.C from a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L space R onto S , then S is Lindelöf.

Proof: Let $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ be an open cover of S . As Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.C, $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i) : i \in I\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . Since R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L, the $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i) : i \in I\}$ has a countable subcover say $S = \{\Psi^{-1}(A_{i_n}) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$. Therefore $R =$

$\bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \psi^{-1}(A^*_{i_n})$, that is $\Psi(R) = S = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} A^*_{i_n}$, where $\{A^*_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a countable subcover for S and so S is Lindelöf.

Theorem 5.19: The image of $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L under $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.I is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L.

Proof: Let Ψ be a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.I from $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L space R onto S . Let $\{A^*_i : i \in I\}$ be a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of S . Then $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i) : i \in I\}$ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R as Ψ is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.I. Since R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L, the $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover $\{\Psi^{-1}(A^*_i) : i \in I\}$ of R has a countable subcover say $\{\Psi^{-1}(A_{i_n}) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$. Thus $R =$

$\bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \psi^{-1}(A^*_{i_n})$ which implies $\Psi(R) = S = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} A_{i_n}$, that is

$\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a countable subfamily of $\{A_i : i \in I\}$. Hence S is Lindelöf.

Theorem 5.20: If R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L and countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, then R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact.

Proof: Suppose R is countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact and $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L and $\{A_i : i \in I\}$ be a $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . As R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$.L, $\{A_i : i \in I\}$ has a countable subcover say $\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

Therefore $\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a countable subcover of R and $\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a subfamily of $\{A_i : i \in I\}$ and so $\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a countable $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -open cover of R . Since R is $\text{C.spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact, $\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ has a finite subcover say $\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\} \subseteq \{A_i : i \in I\}$ and so $\{A_{i_n} : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a finite subcover of $\{A_i : i \in I\}$ for R . Hence R is $\text{spg}\omega\alpha$ -compact.

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